

KINERJA DOSEN: KONTRIBUSINYA TERHADAP AKREDITASI PERGURUAN TINGGI

Wahyudi

Universitas Pamulang, Banten
dosen00716@unpam.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

Being a good lecturer is awareness, but being a responsible lecturer is a demand. In this section, it will be found that many lecturers are not correct in some of their obligations, and this causes the institution's performance to be drop. In this research, it will be stated how the actual lecturer performance, what is the meaning and impact, and what to do next. Qualitative methods are used to see the reality of a phenomenon, and the data becomes authentic evidence, so that it can be suggested implications. The results showed that the lecturers' performance was low, both in education, research, and community service. This emphasizes how lecturers are ignorant of their obligations, how institutional leaders do not care about the situation, and this is normal if the institution's achievement is low.

Keywords: Education, Research, Devotion, Performance, Lecturer

PENDAHULUAN

Hal yang diharapkan dari seorang dosen adalah kinerja dalam Tri Dharma, apa artinya? Seorang dosen melakukan tugasnya dengan benar. Di mana seluruh komponen kewajiban ditunaikan sebagaimana tuntutan, dan dampak dari hal itu adalah keseimbangan antara ilmu pengetahuan dan kontribusi bagi khalayak banyak. Hal ini pun menjadi bukti, bahwa label dosen yang melekat tidak hanya sekedar teori, akan tetapi penegas nyata bahwa berilmu itu dapat memberikan perubahan, baik mencerdaskan maupun menyejahterakan (Aisyah, et, al., 2019).

Dosen adalah profesi yang mengharuskan pelakunya memenuhi tiga dimensi, yakni kecerdasan intelektual, kecerdasan emosional, dan kecerdasan spiritual (Abramovskikh, et, al., 2019). Ketiga hal tersebut penting bagi terwujudnya pelaksanaan Tri Dharma secara baik dan benar, atau disebut juga kohesif. Artinya,